

Assessing the photochemical mineralisation of dissolved organic carbon in lakes

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Photomineralisation rate of dissolved organic matter was modelled in 72,380 lakes.
- Lakes between 60°S and 60°N, at <500 m a.s.l., with depth ≥ 5 m were considered.
- Lakes in the 30°N-60°N latitude belt accounted for most of CO₂ photoproduction.
- Seven large lakes would be responsible for 50 % of CO₂ photogeneration.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Photochemical mineralisation is an abiotic process by which the organic matter in natural waters, which is mostly dissolved, is eventually transformed into CO₂ by the action of sunlight. The process has important implications for global C cycling, the penetration of sunlight into the water column, photochemical reactions, and microbial processes. Here we applied an approximated photochemical model to assess the extent of CO₂ photogeneration by mineralisation of dissolved organic matter in lakes located between 60°S and 60°N latitude. The results suggest that, although lake-water organic matter would usually undergo faster photomineralisation in the tropical belt than elsewhere, by far the highest contributions to the photochemical production of CO₂ would come from lakes located between 30°N and 60°N latitude. In particular, of the $\sim 7 \times 10^4$ lakes we selected for the study, around 50 % of CO₂ photogeneration would be accounted for by just 7 large lakes, of which only one is located in the tropical belt. It appears that the lake surface is a very important factor that affects the overall photomineralisation potential of dissolved organic matter.

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1. Introduction

Organic matter is the pool of diverse organic substances that occur in natural waters. Of these, a major fraction is represented by the dissolved compounds that make up the dissolved organic matter or DOM (Wershaw, 2004; Zark and Dittmar, 2018). DOM occurs in surface waters at concentrations ranging from less than one to around one hundred mgC L⁻¹ (Massicotte et al., 2017). The lower range of DOM molecular weights is accounted for by small molecules, while controversy has arisen about the nature of the DOM fractions with high molecular weight. These might either consist of water-soluble macromolecules, or of micelle-like aggregates of smaller compounds (Guetzloff and Rice, 1994; Jones and Bryan, 1998; Piccolo, 2001). To date, the controversy has not yet reached a clear agreement and each of the two opposing views might well be at least partially correct, with high-molecular weight DOM possibly including both macromolecules and aggregates (Baigorri et al., 2007).

An important DOM fraction is represented by the compounds that contain chromophoric groups and are thus able to absorb sunlight: such fraction is the so-called chromophoric dissolved organic matter or CDOM (Zhang et al., 2021). CDOM is an important sunlight absorber in natural waters, especially at shorter wavelengths (Nebbioso and Piccolo, 2013; Nelson and Siegel, 2013), and it highly affects the penetration of sunlight in the lower depths of water columns (Ahonen et al., 2024; Huovinen et al., 2003). Sunlight absorption by CDOM also has an impact on the transformation of dissolved molecules, including the contaminants (Guo et al., 2023; Rocha et al., 2022). On the one side, CDOM screens sunlight and inhibits direct photolysis processes but, on the other side, radiation absorption by CDOM generates a range of reactive transient species that react with dissolved molecules and contribute to their transformation (Janssen et al., 2014). The process of radiation absorption with the partial involvement of photogenerated transient species also modifies CDOM itself, usually by producing oxidised derivatives such as hydroxylated and carboxylated compounds (Clark et al., 2019; Del Vecchio and Blough, 2002; Goldstone et al., 2002; Grebel et al., 2009). The same process also yields volatile species such as CO and, most notably, CO₂ (Buckley et al., 2024; Salonen and Vähätalo, 1994).

The photomineralisation of (C)DOM, that is, the abiotic process of eventual CO₂ formation upon absorption of sunlight, is a major environmental reaction pathway (Cory et al., 2014; Koehler et al., 2014; Miller and Zepp, 1995). It is part of the global carbon cycle and, although the DOM pool in natural waters is continuously regenerated by opposing processes that include photosynthesis, net carbon gains or losses by aquatic environments on a global scale would significantly affect planetary equilibria (Tranvik et al., 2009). Moreover, considering the important roles of (C)DOM as, among others, sunlight absorber, nutrient for microorganisms, and ligand for metals, including toxic ones, it is clear that the dynamics of organic matter in natural waters raise much scientific interest.

Several studies have addressed the kinetics and pathways by which sunlit natural waters and the organic matter they contain yield CO₂ by photochemical reactions (Cory and Kling, 2018), and estimates of the process efficiency in terms of quantum yields of CO₂ photogeneration are currently available (Vähätalo et al., 2000).

This work has the goal of assessing the photochemical generation of CO₂ by lake water on a very wide (almost global) geographic scale. To do so, we combined information contained in existing databases, calculation procedures for photochemical reactions, and an assessment of sunlight irradiance. In particular, we used:

- (i) Global databases of lakes (Lehner and Messenger, 2016; Messenger et al., 2016; Toming et al., 2020a, 2020b), which provide information about geographical location, depth, surface area, and dissolved organic carbon (DOC).

- (ii) A monochromatic approximation to photoinduced reactions (Vione, 2021; Vione and Carena, 2022), which allows for a considerable simplification of the otherwise very complex multi-wavelength calculations (including most notably the absorption of sunlight by CDOM along the water column), with negligible loss in accuracy.
- (iii) A quasi-global assessment of the spectral photon flux density of sunlight reaching the ground.

The results provide insight into the role of lake photochemistry in the global carbon cycle.

2. Methods

2.1. Study lakes

The dataset of water bodies used for the present study consisted of 72,380 lakes and reservoirs (hereafter, generally referred to as 'lakes') with area ≥ 10 ha, included in the large database HydroLAKES (<http://www.hydrosheds.org>; Lehner and Messenger, 2016; Messenger et al., 2016). We considered the lakes comprised in the latitude belt between 60°S and 60°N, with average depth ≥ 5 m and elevation <500 m a.s.l., for which we were able to estimate sunlight intensity based on geographical coordinates (*vide infra*). The choice criteria are described in the next sections. Dissolved organic carbon (DOC, mgC L⁻¹) data for the selected lakes were from the work of Toming and co-workers (Toming et al., 2020b), who predicted *in situ* DOC of lake water at a global scale (Toming et al., 2020a).

2.2. Monochromatic assessment of organic matter mineralisation in lake water

Previous works have investigated the process of photoinduced transformation of dissolved organic matter into CO₂ (e.g., Buckley et al., 2024; Gu et al., 2017; Vähätalo et al., 2000; Yuan et al., 2019). In particular, the apparent quantum yield of CO₂ photoproduction by irradiated CDOM in lake water has been quantified as $\Phi_{\text{CO}_2}(\lambda) = c \cdot 10^{-d\lambda}$, where $c = 7.5 \text{ mol E}^{-1}$ (E = Einstein = moles of photons) and $d = 0.012 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ (Vähätalo et al., 2000). Such a wavelength trend means that, the longer is the wavelength, the less effective sunlight photons are in inducing DOC photomineralisation, thereby offsetting higher irradiance at longer wavelengths. On this basis, the CO₂ photoproduction rate can be determined from $\Phi_{\text{CO}_2}(\lambda)$ and the spectral solar photon flux density absorbed by CDOM, $p_a^{\text{CDOM}}(\lambda)$ (Braslavsky, 2007; Cory and Kling, 2018):

$$R_{\text{CO}_2} = \int_{\lambda} \Phi_{\text{CO}_2}(\lambda) p_a^{\text{CDOM}}(\lambda) d\lambda = \frac{10 t_{\text{DL}}}{d} \int_{\lambda} \Phi_{\text{CO}_2}(\lambda) p^\circ(\lambda) [1 - 10^{-100A_1(\lambda)d\text{DOC}}] d\lambda \quad (1)$$

where R_{CO_2} has units of [molC L⁻¹ day⁻¹], $\Phi_{\text{CO}_2}(\lambda)$ is as per the above discussion, $p^\circ(\lambda)$ [E cm⁻² s⁻¹ nm⁻¹] is the spectral solar photon flux density incident on the water column (daily average), t_{DL} [s day⁻¹] is the length of the day, d [m] is the average depth of the water column, 10 is the conversion factor between [m⁻¹ cm⁻²] and [L⁻¹], $A_1(\lambda)$ [L mgC⁻¹ cm⁻¹] is the specific absorbance of CDOM (referred to DOC = 1 mgC L⁻¹ and an optical path length of 1 cm), and 100 is the conversion factor between [m] and [cm]. If C_C [molC L⁻¹] is the molar concentration of organic carbon ($C_C = 8.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ DOC}$), the corresponding photomineralisation rate coefficient can be expressed as $k_{\text{CO}_2} = R_{\text{CO}_2} C_C^{-1}$:

$$k_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{10 t_{\text{DL}}}{C_C d} \int_{\lambda} \Phi_{\text{CO}_2}(\lambda) p^\circ(\lambda) [1 - 10^{-100A_1(\lambda)d\text{DOC}}] d\lambda \quad (2)$$

Polychromatic expressions such as that for k_{CO_2} (Eq. 2) can be subjected to a monochromatic approximation (Vione, 2021). Also note that the DOC [mgC L⁻¹] is a much more widespread water parameter compared to C_C . We used the following single-wavelength equation for

k_{CO_2} :

$$k_{\text{CO}_2} [\text{day}^{-1}] = \frac{10p^\circ(\lambda_{\text{eq}})\rho_{\text{CO}_2}t_{\text{DL}}}{d\text{DOC}} \left[1 - 10^{-100A_1(\lambda_{\text{eq}})d\text{DOC}}\right] \quad (3)$$

where λ_{eq} [nm] is the equivalent monochromatic wavelength that allows Eq. (3) to approximate the polychromatic Eq. (2); ρ_{CO_2} [mgC nm E⁻¹] is the photon efficiency of CO₂ photoproduction, which takes into account the C_C–DOC conversion and the fact that CDOM absorbs lesser radiation at λ_{eq} than in the whole λ interval (Vione, 2021). The other parameters are the same as in Eqs. (1) and (2). Moreover, in Eqs. (1)–(3) we used average values for $A_1(\lambda)$ in lake water ($A_1(\lambda) = A_0 e^{-S\lambda}$, where $A_0 = 0.45 \text{ L mgC}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $S = 0.015 \text{ nm}^{-1}$) (Vione and Carena, 2022).

The monochromatic approximation needs a fit procedure of Eq. (2) data with Eq. (3). To do so, we followed the recommendations of a previous work (Vione, 2021) that the value of $A_1(\lambda_{\text{eq}})$ is the most critical for the identification of λ_{eq} . At this stage our calculations are referred to midday on the spring equinox, at 45°N latitude. As recommended, we carried out a three-step procedure as follows (d was varied from 5 to 30 m to be representative of the studied lakes, *vide infra*):

(i) Fit the Eq. (2) results (k_{CO_2} vs. DOC for $d = 15 \text{ m}$, intermediate case) with Eq. (3), letting three free-floating parameters ($p^\circ(\lambda_{\text{eq}})$, $A_1(\lambda_{\text{eq}})$, and ρ_{CO_2}) and fixing d and t_{DL} . From the fit we obtained, in particular, $A_1(\lambda_{\text{eq}}) = 9.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mgC}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which suggests that $\lambda_{\text{eq}} = 410 \text{ nm}$ (Vione, 2021).

(ii) Fix the values of $A_1(\lambda_{\text{eq}})$ as previously obtained and of $p^\circ(\lambda_{\text{eq}})$ ($1.9 \times 10^{-10} \text{ E cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ for 410 nm; Frank and Klöpffer, 1988), leaving ρ_{CO_2} as the only free-floating parameter in the new fit (again, for $d = 15 \text{ m}$). By so doing, we obtained $\rho_{\text{CO}_2} = 190 \text{ mgC nm E}^{-1}$.

(iii) With the value $\rho_{\text{CO}_2} = 190 \text{ mgC nm E}^{-1}$ (as well as $A_1(\lambda_{\text{eq}}) = 9.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mgC}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $p^\circ(\lambda_{\text{eq}}) = 1.9 \times 10^{-10} \text{ E cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ nm}^{-1}$), use Eq. (3) to calculate k_{CO_2} for $d = 5, 10, 20$, and 30 m .

Fig. 1 (red squares) shows the predictions of polychromatic Eq. (2) for the spring equinox at 45°N latitude, for different values of average water-column depth and DOC. Note that $t_{\text{DL}} = 43,200 \text{ s day}^{-1}$, *i.e.*, 12 h daylight and 12 h night as per the equinox conditions. Moreover, water depths at $d > 30 \text{ m}$ would be totally or almost totally in the dark, for which reason d values above 30 m were not considered.

The results obtained with Eq. (3) are shown as dashed curves in Fig. 1. A generally good to very good agreement between polychromatic

Fig. 1. Calculated values of k_{CO_2} , for different average water depths and DOC values. The squares represent polychromatic calculations (Eq. 2), while the dashed curves are the assessment carried out with the monochromatic approximation (Eq. 3). The normalised mean root square error between monochromatic and polychromatic calculations was typically $<1\%$, with the single exception of $d = 5 \text{ m}$ and $\text{DOC} = 1 \text{ mgC L}^{-1}$ ($\sim 17\%$). Well-mixed water conditions are assumed. Sunlight irradiance: noon, 45°N, clear sky, spring equinox.

Eq. (2) and monochromatic Eq. (3) was obtained (normalised mean root square error often $<1\%$). The highest error ($\sim 17\%$) was observed at one extreme of the variation range, for $d = 5 \text{ m}$ and $\text{DOC} = 1 \text{ mgC L}^{-1}$.

The use of Eq. (3) for a wide-scale assessment of k_{CO_2} requires the knowledge of d (average lake depth) and DOC (both d and DOC are currently available for lake water at a global scale; Lehner and Messenger, 2016; Messenger et al., 2016; Toming et al., 2020a, 2020b), as well as of $p^\circ(\lambda_{\text{eq}} = 410 \text{ nm})$ and day length (*vide infra* for their calculation as a function of latitude and day of the year). Other important quantities that can be derived from k_{CO_2} are:

(i) The photomineralisation rate R'_{CO_2} on a [mgC L⁻¹ day⁻¹] basis (note that [mgC L⁻¹] = [gC m⁻³]):

$$R'_{\text{CO}_2} [\text{gC m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}] = k_{\text{CO}_2} \text{DOC} \quad (4)$$

(ii) The photomineralisation rate per unit lake surface area, $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{S}}$ (with average depth d in [m] as usual):

$$R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{S}} [\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}] = R'_{\text{CO}_2} d \quad (5)$$

(iii) The rate of organic matter mineralisation in the whole lake, $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$:

$$R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}} [\text{gC day}^{-1}] = R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{S}} S_{\text{L}} = k_{\text{CO}_2} \text{DOC} d S_{\text{L}} \quad (6)$$

where S_{L} is the surface area of the lake, expressed in [m²].

2.3. Limits and uncertainties of the model

The model approach we used has unavoidable limitations, many of which derive from the number and type of parameters that are currently known/available for the global lakes. First of all, the DOC assessment by Toming et al. (2020a, 2020b) used a machine-learning approach that would be affected by uncertainty. The relative standard deviation, expressed as $\sigma_{\text{DOC}} \text{DOC}^{-1}$, would usually be below 0.5, with most likely values around 0.1–0.2 for the studied lakes (Carena et al., 2023). Note that seasonal DOC variations were not considered, thus the relevant DOC values should be intended as year averages.

Furthermore, water absorption spectra (mainly accounted for by CDOM in this framework) might be taken into account in calculations but, unfortunately, they are not available for the very vast majority of the investigated lakes. Therefore, typical (average) values were considered for the specific absorbance of CDOM, as $A_1(\lambda = 410 \text{ nm}) = A_0 e^{-410S}$, with $A_0 = 0.45 \text{ L mgC}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $S = 0.015 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ as mentioned before. Such an approach is not always successful to predict actual values of the specific absorbance and could introduce significant biases when dealing with near-surface photochemical reactivity (Partanen et al., 2021). However, here we considered whole water columns of lakes ($d \geq 5 \text{ m}$) that would usually absorb the vast majority of incident radiation, independently of the $A_1(\lambda)$ values. Actually, lakes with very different $A_1(\lambda)$ values would mainly differ in that the same radiation would be absorbed in a near-surface layer when $A_1(\lambda)$ is high, and in an important fraction of the water column when $A_1(\lambda)$ is low. However, integrated absorption along the whole water column would be similar in both cases (Partanen et al., 2021). Considering that here we took into account whole water columns of lakes, the approximation used for $A_1(\lambda = 410 \text{ nm})$ would most likely introduce lesser biases compared to other factors that are detailed below.

The type and origin of organic matter would also play a significant role in photoreactivity (De Laurentiis et al., 2012), but this kind of information was not available for the global lakes. Again, here we considered average CDOM properties. It should also be remarked that pedogenic organic matter usually absorbs sunlight to a higher extent compared to the aquagenic one, but the absorbance of CDOM often correlates negatively with its intrinsic photoreactivity to produce a partial compensation effect (Du et al., 2024). Actually, aromatic-rich (C) DOM of terrestrial origin usually undergoes more extensive photoinduced mineralisation, but with lower quantum yields, compared to (C)

DOM types containing higher fractions of saturated compounds (Milstead et al., 2023).

Photochemistry calculations can deal with the case of stratified lakes, treating epilimnion and hypolimnion as separate environments, provided that the thermocline depth is available (Calderaro and Vione, 2020). However, such data are not known for the global lakes and we had thus to assume well-mixed water columns. On the one side, photoreactions are less efficient in stratified lakes compared to mixing ones (Apell et al., 2020), thus our approximation might lead to an overestimate of photomineralisation rates. On the other side, the difference between stratified and well-mixed waters is particularly marked only in

$$p_{\text{sn}}^{\circ}(410 \text{ nm}) = I_{\text{AM0}}(410 \text{ nm}) \exp\left(\frac{-\kappa(410 \text{ nm})}{\cos(\phi - \delta) + 0.506(96.08 + \phi - \delta)^{-1.636}}\right) \frac{410}{hcN_a} \quad (7)$$

the case of fast photoreactions that induce substrate disappearance in the sunlit epilimnion (Vione and Scozzaro, 2019). Considering that the transformation of CDOM into CO_2 is a relatively slow process (Vione et al., 2009), assuming a well-mixed water column would not introduce a huge bias.

Water turbidity caused by suspended solids modifies the underwater light field, increasing the near-surface irradiance and decreasing that in the lower depths (Loiselle et al., 2015). In addition to the mathematical difficulties in treating turbidity, no estimate of this parameter is currently available for the global lakes. However, the impact of this knowledge gap is reduced by two issues: (i) the role of turbidity is less important when dealing with whole water columns or average water-column values, as it is the case here. Indeed, a clear-water approximation underestimates irradiance at the surface but overestimates it in deep water, with partial compensation (Loiselle et al., 2015). (ii) The exclusion of the shallowest lakes ($d < 5$ m, accounting for about 27 % of the total lake area in the considered latitude belt) was specifically intended to limit the weight of turbidity in calculations, because deep lakes are typically characterised by clearer waters (Wetzel, 2001).

The effects on the underwater light field due to ice cover were not included in calculations and, for this reason, our model did not consider lakes located above 500 m a.s.l. (around 12 % of the total) that are more likely to be covered with ice during part of the year. Our photoreactivity results could be overestimated in high-latitude lakes that may be covered by ice during the cold season, even if they are located below 500 m a.s.l. For those lakes, it has been estimated that DOC photomineralisation rates would be decreased by about 20–25 % due to ice cover (Koehler et al., 2014).

Our model also considers clear-sky conditions, thereby providing an upper limit for photochemical reaction kinetics. Cloud cover could decrease photoreaction rates by up to 40 %–50 % in some equatorial areas and in East Asia (Partanen and McNeill, 2023).

Ice cover, water temperature, lake stratification, and cloud cover might be deeply impacted in the future by climatic changes (Neale et al., 2021), and all these issues might potentially affect organic-matter photomineralisation. At the moment these phenomena cannot be taken into account to assess future evolutions of the photomineralisation reactions, but the above discussion provides some insight into their possible importance.

In this framework, the monochromatic approximation used to assess the photogeneration of CO_2 (Eq. (3) vs. Eq. (2)) would introduce a very limited bias, which would be negligible in most cases (relative error < 1 %, Fig. 1) and could only reach moderate significance for low-depth and low-DOC environments (relative error up to 17 %, Fig. 1).

Finally, the limitations in the latitude interval (60°S – 60°N) are linked to length-of-day calculation issues (see section 3.1).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Quasi-global assessment of sunlight intensity at 410 nm and its validation

To apply the monochromatic approximation on a wide geographic scale, one should assess $p^{\circ}(410 \text{ nm})$ (spectral photon flux density, daily average) as a function of day and latitude. First of all, the incident spectral photon flux density of sunlight at the solar noon ($p_{\text{sn}}^{\circ}(410 \text{ nm})$, units of $\text{E cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-1}$) can be computed as follows (Moreno-SanSegundo et al., 2021):

where I_{AM0} is the intensity of sunlight outside the atmosphere ($I_{\text{AM0}}(410 \text{ nm}) = 1.54 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{nm}^{-1}$), κ is the atmospheric extinction coefficient ($\kappa(410 \text{ nm}) = 0.255 \text{ AM}^{-1}$), ϕ is the latitude ($60^{\circ}\text{S} (-60^{\circ}) < \phi < 60^{\circ}\text{N} (+60^{\circ})$), $\delta = 23.45^{\circ} \sin\left(\frac{360}{365}(\text{day} + 284)\right)$ is the Sun's declination ($\text{day} = 1$ is 1st January, $\text{day} = 365$ is 31st December), h is Planck's constant, c is light's speed in vacuum, and N_a is Avogadro's number.

On this basis, the daily dose reaching the Earth's surface can be calculated as follows (García-Gil et al., 2022):

$$G_{\text{day}}(410 \text{ nm}) = F_1 p_{\text{sn}}^{\circ}(410 \text{ nm}) \tau_{\text{DL}} = \int_{1\text{day}} p^{\circ}(410 \text{ nm}) dt \quad (8)$$

where F_1 is a constant proportionality factor (*vide infra*) and $\tau_{\text{DL}} = \frac{2}{15} \arccos(-\tan(\phi)\tan(\delta))$ is the day length in hours (the value of the arccos is in degrees). Note that such an assessment of τ_{DL} is only possible between 60°S and 60°N latitude, which accounts for the latitude limits of the lakes in this study.

We first considered $\phi = 45^{\circ}\text{N}$ and computed the integral $\int_{1\text{day}} p^{\circ}(410 \text{ nm}, t) dt$ for the 15th day of each month, introducing for each hour of the day the zenith angle obtained with the Solar Position Algorithm

Fig. 2. Fit for the daily dose during the year for a latitude of 45°N . The solid squares represent the values integrated along the 15th day of each month. The solid curve shows the values predicted by Eq. (8) ($G_{\text{day}}(410 \text{ nm}) = F_1 p_{\text{sn}}^{\circ}(410 \text{ nm}) \tau_{\text{DL}}$, with $F_1 = 0.73$).

from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Solar Position Algorithm| NREL. [WWW Document], 2022). The results of the integral calculations are shown as squares in Fig. 2. Such data were interpolated with the fit function $G_{\text{day}}(410 \text{ nm}) = F_1 p_{\text{sn}}^\circ(410 \text{ nm}) \tau_{\text{DL}}$, with day as independent variable (involved in the expressions of δ and, as a consequence, τ_{DL}), and F_1 as the only free-floating parameter. The fit function is shown as a solid curve in Fig. 2.

From the numerical fit we obtained $F_1 = 0.73$ with a normalised mean root square error of 2.8 %. It is clearly $F_1 < 1$, because $p_{\text{sn}}^\circ(410 \text{ nm})$ at noon is the maximum value of the spectral photon flux density reached by sunlight in each day, while the integral $\int_{1\text{day}} p^\circ(410 \text{ nm}, t) dt$ takes into account the spectral photon flux density from sunrise to sunset.

It would be convenient to apply $F_1 = 0.73$ on a global scale. In this framework, the same integral calculations as per Fig. 2 ($G_{\text{day}}(410 \text{ nm}) = \int_{1\text{day}} p^\circ(410 \text{ nm}, t) dt$) were carried out for latitudes ranging from 60°S to 60°N at steps of 5°, and it was also computed $G_{\text{day}}(410 \text{ nm}) = 0.73 p_{\text{sn}}^\circ(410 \text{ nm}) \tau_{\text{DL}}$. Integral calculation results are reported in Fig. 3 as solid symbols, while $G_{\text{day}}(410 \text{ nm}) = 0.73 p_{\text{sn}}^\circ(410 \text{ nm}) \tau_{\text{DL}}$ is reported as solid curves. Note that such curves do not represent the results of data

Fig. 3. Validation of the daily dose calculations as a function of the latitude and the day of the year (curves: calculated daily dose; solid symbols: integrated daily dose). (A) Latitudes from 0° to 60°N with steps of 5°. (B) Latitudes from 60°S to 0°.

fit because, once $F_1 = 0.73$ is fixed, the calculation of $G_{\text{day}}(410 \text{ nm})$ can be done for each day of the year in the whole latitude belt from 60°S to 60°N. The normalised mean root square error between integral calculations and curve points was in the range of 3 to 11 %, which justifies the use of our calculation approach.

Upon application of this procedure Eq. (3) gets modified as follows, where $F_1 p_{\text{sn}}^\circ(410 \text{ nm})$ replaces $p^\circ(410 \text{ nm})$ and τ_{DL} can be calculated as per the above discussion (also note that t_{DL} in Eq. (3) is expressed in [s day^{-1}], while here τ_{DL} is in [h day^{-1}]):

$$k_{\text{CO}_2} [\text{day}^{-1}] = 3.5 \times 10^3 \arccos(-\tan(\phi)\tan(\delta)) \frac{p_{\text{sn}}^\circ(410 \text{ nm}) \rho_{\text{CO}_2}}{d \text{DOC}} \left[1 - 10^{-100 A_1 (\lambda_{\text{eq}}) d \text{DOC}} \right] \quad (9)$$

where $3.5 \times 10^3 = 3600 \cdot 2/15 \cdot 10 \cdot 0.73$. Eq. (9) allows for the calculation of the photomineralisation rate coefficient k_{CO_2} for all the selected lakes located between 60°S and 60°N latitude.

3.2. Photomineralisation assessment on a wide geographic scale

On the basis of the previous discussion, Eq. (9) was used to assess photomineralisation kinetics. The results for k_{CO_2} are shown in Fig. 4 as year averages, and the data suggest that k_{CO_2} could reach up to $3.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$. In this case, it would take around 200 days to photochemically transform into CO_2 half of the organic matter originally occurring in lake water. It can be seen from the figure that the lakes located between 30°S and 30°N latitude would often feature quite high k_{CO_2} values. This behaviour has two main explanations: (i) clear-sky sunlight irradiance is higher in the tropics compared to higher northern or southern latitudes, although along the equator, the often extensive cloud cover would decrease actual irradiance by around 30 % (García-Gil et al., 2022; Partanen and McNeill, 2023); (ii) tropical lakes often have relatively low DOC values (see Fig. 5 in Carena et al., 2023, for a DOC map of the lake database we used and Töming et al., 2020a, for a more general map of lake-water DOC) and, as shown in Fig. 1, k_{CO_2} decreases as the DOC increases.

Once k_{CO_2} is determined, other parameters can be computed, such as R'_{CO_2} (photomineralisation rate) by means of Eq. (4). The relevant map of R'_{CO_2} is reported in Fig. 5. It is interesting to observe that, once again, the production of CO_2 per unit volume would often be faster between 30°S and 30°N latitude than elsewhere. However, many high-DOC lakes located above 30°N latitude feature a slightly lower but still relatively high CO_2 photogeneration rate (around $4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ gC m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$). Note that $R'_{\text{CO}_2} = k_{\text{CO}_2} \text{DOC}$ (Eq. (4)), thus under high-DOC conditions, the low k_{CO_2} values (Fig. 1) would be offset by elevated DOC.

The reference database we used (Töming et al., 2020b) does not address the issue of long-term trends of the DOC parameter. In some Nordic environments such as the Scandinavian peninsula, the DOC values of surface waters are gradually increasing (and will continue doing so in the future; Weyhenmeyer et al., 2016) due to the so-called browning phenomenon, which is partially linked with increasing precipitation due to climatic changes. However, the same trend is not being observed in other regions of the world such as the USA (Jane et al., 2017), thus future DOC variations in freshwaters are still an open issue that warrants investigation.

A surface-normalised rate is often reported to quantify photomineralisation in lake water. This is the $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{S}}$ parameter given by Eq. (5) and, in our quasi-global assessment, $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{S}}$ ranged between roughly 1.2×10^{-2} and $2.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$. Such values are equivalent to 1000–2000 $\mu\text{molC m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$, which is in the typical range reported for lakes and assessed on the basis of irradiation experiments carried out with real water samples (Vähätalo et al., 2021).

The variation range of $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{S}}$ is quite limited, most likely because $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{S}} = k_{\text{CO}_2} \text{DOC} d$, with the consequence that the decrease of k_{CO_2} with increasing d and DOC (Fig. 1) is offset by the need to multiply k_{CO_2} by

Fig. 4. Map of k_{CO_2} (year average) for the lakes under study. The map was made by means of the software QGIS (QGIS, 2020).

Fig. 5. Map of $R'_{CO_2} = k_{CO_2} \text{ DOC}$ (year average) for the lakes under study. The map was made by means of the software QGIS (QGIS, 2020).

DOC and d to obtain $R_{CO_2}^S$. A previous model assessment has estimated an average $R_{CO_2}^S = 3.8 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ in $\sim 10^3$ Swedish lakes located between 55°N and 69°N . Such a value would increase by 26 % and by 33 % when neglecting the effects of, respectively, ice-cover (very important at those latitudes during the cold season) and water turbidity (Koehler et al., 2014). Our model predicted an average $R_{CO_2}^S = 6.9 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (i.e., $1.9 \times 10^{-2} \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) for $\sim 1.7 \times 10^3$ Swedish lakes located in the 55°N - 60°N latitude belt, in good agreement with previous results.

Finally, the overall contribution of a lake to CO_2 photogeneration is

quantified as $R_{CO_2}^{\text{lake}}$ (Eq. (6)), which depends on the lake volume ($V = d S_L$) in addition to the photoactivity of lake water per unit volume ($R'_{CO_2} = k_{CO_2} \text{ DOC}$). The $R_{CO_2}^{\text{lake}}$ map is shown in Fig. 6, suggesting that many of the lakes emitting $>10^7 \text{ gC day}^{-1}$ would be located in the American continent and, particularly, in North America. Interestingly, the interplay between intrinsic (per unit volume) lake-water photoactivity (R'_{CO_2}) and total lake volume produced differences of up to six orders of magnitude in $R_{CO_2}^{\text{lake}} = R'_{CO_2} d S_L$, where volume played the main role in the observed variability: note that the R'_{CO_2} range in Fig. 5 is

Fig. 6. Map of $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}} = k_{\text{CO}_2} \text{DOC} d S_L$ (year average) for the lakes under study. The map was made by means of the software QGIS (QGIS, 2020).

Fig. 7. Latitude distribution of the cumulated $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$ values.

much narrower than the range of $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$ in Fig. 6.

Fig. 7 shows the cumulated $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$ values in each latitude belt (sums of $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$ for all the study lakes located in each latitude interval). Very interestingly, the $\sim 7 \times 10^4$ lakes we selected from the database would produce a total of $\sim 2.8 \times 10^{10}$ gC day $^{-1}$ CO $_2$, of which roughly 50 % would be accounted for by just seven large lakes: Caspian Sea (Iran, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Russia), Lake Baikal (Russia), Lakes Superior, Michigan, Huron, Erie (USA, Canada), and Lake Malawi (Malawi, Mozambique, Tanzania). With the exception of Lake Malawi, all the others are located in the 30°N-60°N latitude belt and, unsurprisingly, lakes from this belt would account for the vast majority of the cumulated $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$ (Fig. 7). Another issue is that the seven large lakes mentioned above constitute a mere 0.01 % of the total number of study lakes, but account for around 50 % of the total cumulated lake surface (Messenger et al., 2016).

The close correspondence between the fractions of total surface and of total $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$ (~ 50 % in both cases) is likely accounted for by the fact that

$R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$ (surface-normalised CO $_2$ generation) had a very narrow range of variation (a factor of 2, see above).

The $\sim 7 \times 10^4$ lakes selected for this study have a total cumulated surface area of 1.3×10^6 km 2 , while all the lakes of the original database located between 60°S and 60°N (for a total of around 7.1×10^5 lakes) have an overall surface area of 2.2×10^6 km 2 (Messenger et al., 2016). It should also be considered that the database only includes lakes with surface area > 10 ha, while lakes having surface areas ranging between 1 and 10 ha could be an order of magnitude more numerous (Messenger et al., 2016). It is estimated that, by including such lakes, the total cumulated surface area could increase by a further 20 % (Messenger et al., 2016).

On this basis, under the hypotheses that $R_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{lake}}$ is roughly proportional to the lake surface, and that the lakes we excluded from photochemical modelling produce CO $_2$ to a comparable extent as the lakes we selected, it could be tentatively assumed that lakes larger than 1 ha and located between 60°S and 60°N might produce 6×10^{10} gC day $^{-1}$ (i.e., 20 MtC year $^{-1}$) of CO $_2$ through the photomineralisation process.

To make a comparison, that would be around 10 % of the flux of organic carbon that is transported each year by the global rivers to the oceans (Cai, 2011). Interestingly, this value is in quite good agreement with a previous estimate that extrapolated the photochemical behaviour of Swedish lakes on a global scale. By so doing, it was predicted ~ 30 MtC year $^{-1}$ of inorganic carbon produced under clear-sky conditions by global lakes located between 60°S and 80°N latitude (Koehler et al., 2014). On the one side, our estimated 20 MtC year $^{-1}$ of CO $_2$ are not net emissions, because lake water also incorporates atmospheric CO $_2$ by processes such as photosynthesis. On the other side, however, any changes in the biogeochemical processes that may induce a net transformation of lake organic carbon into CO $_2$, or *vice versa*, would have significant effects on the carbon cycle. To make an instance, based on Fig. 4, photomineralisation alone would have the potential to deplete half of the lake-water DOC in a time scale ranging from 200 days to 30 years, depending on the environment.

4. Conclusions

We applied an approximated photochemical model to assess the generation of CO₂ by photomineralisation of dissolved organic matter in lake water. By using databases that report average depth, surface area, and DOC values of global lakes, we were able to assess photomineralisation kinetics in the latitude interval ranging from 60°S to 60°N (this range is accounted for by the calculation procedure used to obtain the day length τ_{DL}). From the database, we additionally excluded lakes for which photochemistry modelling would likely be less accurate: very shallow lakes ($d < 5$ m), potentially affected by high turbidity, and lakes located above 500 m a.s.l. that could be covered by ice in an important part of the year.

The model results suggest that the photoreactivity of organic matter per unit volume of lake water (yearly averages) would be particularly high in the tropical belt, where the clear-sky irradiance of sunlight is the highest. However, when considering the overall photochemical generation of CO₂ by each lake ($R_{CO_2}^{lake}$), it turned out that around 50 % of the cumulated $R_{CO_2}^{lake}$ between 60°S and 60°N would be accounted for by just seven large lakes (Caspian Sea, Baikal, Superior, Michigan, Huron, Erie, and Malawi), which also account for ~50 % of the overall surface. Of these seven lakes, six are located in the 30°N-60°N latitude belt. The lakes located between 30°N-60°N would also account for the vast majority of CO₂ photogeneration, due to the combination of lake numbers, DOC values, and average size.

The photochemical mineralisation of lake water would be a significant component of the global C cycle. While photomineralisation is usually offset by organic matter photogeneration by, e.g., photosynthesis, imbalances between CO₂ fixation and photoemission might have significant effects on the carbon budget and, as far as organic matter in lake-water is concerned, also on sunlight penetration in the water columns, photochemical reactions, and microbial processes.

Finally, this study focused on the photochemical mineralisation pathway. Additional formation of CO₂ would take place as a consequence of bacterial respiration, which was not taken into account here but should be considered in future studies to get a comprehensive overview of the potential of lake water to emit CO₂.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luca Carena: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ángela García-Gil:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Javier Marugán:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Davide Vione:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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opinions expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, nor can the European Union be held responsible for them.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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